

Vanadium. Part VI. Vanadium (IV) Complexes of Guanylalkyl- and Guanylalkoxyalkyl-ureas

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Several vanadium(IV) complexes of guanylalkyl- and guanylalkoxyalkyl-ureas have been prepared. The complexes conform to the formula $[\text{VO}(\text{Gau})_2]$, where GauH = a molecule of the ligand. The substances are paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=1.67\text{-}1.69$ B.M.).

A novel method of synthesis of guanylalkylureas have recently been described by Dutta and Ray¹. This has made possible a comprehensive study of the co-ordination complexes of copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(III), chromium(III), and palladium (II)² with these ligands. The guanylalkylureas behave very much like the biguanides and substituted biguanides.

We have now succeeded in preparing vanadium(IV) complexes with some of these ligands. When vanadyl sulphate and guanylalkylureas in large excess are mixed together and the medium is made alkaline, there appears a silky, bluish green to rose-violet crystalline precipitate. On drying and analysing, these correspond to the formula $[\text{VO}(\text{Gau})_2]$ (where GauH = a molecule of the guanylalkylurea). The complexes are all paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=1.67\text{-}1.69$ B.M.), indicative of quadrivalence of vanadium.

TABLE I

Magnetic measurements.

Compound.	$\chi_M(\text{corr.})$.	Diamagnetic correction.	$\mu_{\text{eff.}}$ (B.M.)	Temp.
$[\text{VO}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{N}_4\text{O}_2)_2]$	1163×10^{-6}	88.4×10^{-6}	1.67	26°
$[\text{VO}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{N}_4\text{O}_2)_2]$	1166	112.1	1.68	32°
$[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2)_2]$	1160	159.5	1.67	26°
$[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2)_2]$	1185	209.0	1.69	33°

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1. This Journal, 1959, 36, 499.

2. Dutta and Ray, *ibid.*, 1958, 36, 567, 576; Dutta, *ibid.*, 1960, 37, 499; Dutta et al., *ibid.*, 1960, 37, 565, 573; Dutta and Lahiry, *ibid.*, 1960, 37, 789; 1961, 38, 689.

Vanadium(IV) complexes of biguanide and some substituted biguanides have been described by Banerjee and Rây². These resemble the present guanylethylurea complexes in colour, properties, and magnetic moments.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagents were prepared by following the methods of Dutta and Rây¹ and of Dutta and Lahiry².

Oxo-bis-guanylmethylurea-vanadium (IV).—Concentrated aqueous solutions of VOSO_4 (0.2 g. in 2-4 ml water) and guanylmethylurea sulphate (1.7 g. in 10-15 ml water) were mixed. The clear bluish green solution formed was treated with gradual addition of dilute NaOH (ca. 2*N*) solution. The colour first changed to light brownish green with separation of a gelatinous precipitate, probably due to separation of vanadyl hydroxide which, however, passed into solution in excess of alkali (pH ca. 9) producing a heavy bluish green solution. This latter soon afterwards deposited glistening, silky, bluish green crystals which were cooled in ice-water, filtered, washed well with water, and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 . {Found: N, 37.68; V, 17.20. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_4\text{O})_2]$ requires N, 37.71; V, 17.17%}.

Oxo-bis-guanylethylurea-vanadium (IV) was prepared by following the method described above. The product is bluish green in colour. {Found: N, 34.48; V, 15.50. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{N}_4\text{O})_2]$ requires N, 34.46; V, 15.69%}.

Oxo-bis-guanylbutylurea-vanadium (IV).—An aqueous solution of VOSO_4 (0.2 g.) was added to an aqueous solution of guanylbutylurea sulphate (1.8-2 g. in 10-15 ml water) when a bluish green solution was formed. A dilute NaOH solution (ca. 2*N*) was then added to the cooled bluish green solution dropwise when the colour changed successively to light rose-violet, light brown, and light violet with separation of a rose-violet crystalline product in strongly alkaline medium. The mixture was cooled in ice-water, filtered, washed well with cold water, and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 . {Found: N, 29.40; V, 13.20. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2]$ requires N, 29.39; V, 13.38%}.

Oxo-bis-guanylethoxyethylurea-vanadium (IV) was prepared as the preceding one. Here the colour of the solution changed from bluish green to sky-blue at about pH 8-9 with separation of a little of the oily sky-blue substance. The oil was washed repeatedly with water when it solidified to a sky-blue product which was filtered, washed well with water, and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 . {Found: N, 27.20; V, 12.15. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2]$ requires N, 27.11; V, 12.35%}.

Oxo-bis-guanylbutoxyethylurea-vanadium (IV) was prepared in a similar way as the preceding compounds. The colour of the product is light grey-violet. {Found: N, 23.92; V, 10.58. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2]$ requires N, 23.38; V, 10.87%}.